

USOQS guideline document

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1. Introduction

Far from being an exhaustive guideline this document intends to summarize some of the results achieved within the project named Ultra-Stable Optical oscillators from Quantum coherent and entangled Systems (USOQS), to provide a guideline highlighting successes and pit fall we faced toward the realization of different kind of enhanced optical clocks.

The short term stability of optical clocks (either based on atom or ions) is generally limited by fundamental noise, either shot noise or laser phase noise. Better stability is a highly desirable feature of clocks from all point of view, to accelerate the redefinition of the SI second as well as to enable new clock applications in sensing and fundamental physics applications (e.g. clock-based geodesy, dark matter detection fundamental constant time variation). A possible way to improve clock stability, is to exploit advanced quantum technologies capable of achieving noise performances below the Standard Quantum Limit. The overall objective of this project was to study how to deal with quantum coherent and entangled systems in the optical domain to enable a new generation of ultra-stable optical oscillators capable of taking advantage of quantum properties of light and matter. During the project new theoretical and experimental protocols were developed to allow exploitation of quantum techniques in optical clocks, also important steps were achieved in the realization of active optical clocks based on superradiance emission and toward the realization of scalable ion traps to realize entangled multi ion systems.

This document is divided in different section each one of them discussing a specific approach to address the problem. In section 2 we report some consideration on the use of Quantum Non Demolition measurement protocol in optical lattice clocks. In section 3 we report our results in the realization of entangled ions, together with some consideration regarding the technical problems connected with laser noise to realize high-fidelity entanglement and precision spectroscopy with optical qubits in trapped ions. In section 4 we report some indication about the stability performances achievable with active optical clocks. In section 5 we discuss theoretical protocols developed for the implementation of quantum enhanced states using Rabi and Ramsey spectroscopy.

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2. Cavity-enhanced optical lattice clocks

2.1 Quantum Nondemolition measurement protocols for optical lattice clocks

Atoms placed inside an optical cavity experience an enhanced atom-light coupling due to the Purcell effect. This results in a more efficient measurement. OLCs can benefit from this situation when a cavity is used to create the trapping and probing light potentials. In particular, we have investigated a protocol that uses multiple Quantum Nondemolition (QND) measurements of the ground state population of the clock transition of an atomic ensemble inside an optical cavity to overcome the quantum projection noise and reduce the noise of laser detuning estimates obtained in Rabi spectroscopy. The method is thus directly applicable to state-of-the-art OLCs as presently employed. We describe the quantum and classical statistics of atoms and probe light to second order, to obtain analytic results and optimization under several scenarios within the Gaussian approximation.

For realistic QND detection parameters in current OLCs (as the one developed in the WP1 of the USOQS consortium), we predict generation of squeezed states and a metrological improvement of 7.9 dB relative to the best possible frequency stability with projective measurements.

Protocol -. We assume an ensemble of N atoms is prepared by optical pumping in the ground state of the clock transition, and allow for fluctuations in the atom number due to the random processes involved in loading the trapped atoms. The clock laser drives the transition causing the spin state to execute Rabi oscillations with frequency Ω . A set of QND measurements of the output probing light quadrature $X_{\text{out}}^{(i)}$ is performed at times t_i , with a given number of photons $|\alpha_i|^2$ in each measurement. We use the set of measurement outcomes $\{X_{\text{out}}^{(i)}\}$ to build an estimator $\delta_{\text{(est)}}$ for the clock laser detuning δ . The main results of the study are summarized in Fig. 2.1.

Figure 2.1: (left) Sensitivity of the QND measurement protocol. Lines show the Mean Squared Error (MSE) of the laser detuning as a function of the drive laser detuning. The number of atoms is 2×10^4 . Atom-light coupling $g = 3 \times 10^{-7}$ rad/atom. The solid green curve shows the results for the reference protocol defining the standard quantum limit. The dashed curves show the results of the proposed protocol using three-measurements with different timing and number of photons per measurement. The inset shows the MSE with the timings corresponding to the orange protocol (i.e., same measurement timing, and equal measurement pulses) at the optimum detuning $\delta_0/\Omega = 0.6$ for varying measurement strength (photon number for each measurement pulse) parametrized by the fraction of atoms η that suffers incoherent scattering during the protocol. (right) Numerical results of the averaged single shot estimator variance $\epsilon[\text{MSE}(\delta)]$ as a function of the clock laser phase noise parameter γ , with the same color coding as in the left panel.

3. Entanglement-enhanced ion clocks

In entanglement operation on optical qubits in ions in a cooled string (or crystal) stored in a single trapping potential in a linear ion trap, the correlation is communicated via the shared motion. Coherent manipulation of the qubits and motional states utilizes a qubit laser system, similar to a clock laser system, interacting directly with the qubit carrier transition or on the motional sidebands. These systems include fully agile control of intensity, phase, and frequency of the fixed frequency ultrastable cw laser light to cover addressing of all Zeeman states, micromotion sidebands and motional sidebands with one laser for entanglement as well as precision spectroscopy on the

transitions. This enables to keep control of the optical phase during and in between entanglement and precision spectroscopy steps. Entanglement can be scaled up by adding more ions to the string, or when using segmented linear ion traps, by ion transfer between different traps with splitting and shuttling operations followed by further entanglement steps [Kie02, Kau17, Kau17a]. Many demonstrations of operations have been carried out, mostly in quantum computation and simulation experiments, covering radiofrequency Zeeman, hyperfine microwave, or optical qubit transitions. The goal in USOQS was the work on such schemes with high-fidelity entanglement and precision spectroscopy addressed in WP 2 and deliverable D9. To this end the Mølmer-Sørensen gate [Mol99, Roo08] was utilized at LUH on a pair of $^{40}\text{Ca}^+$ ions and at NPL on a pair of $^{88}\text{Sr}^+$ ions with 95(3) % and 96(3) % fidelity, respectively, achieved to date. In both cases a major limiting factor has been identified in the frequency noise or fluctuations between the qubit and the laser source. In part these originate from the use of Zeeman transitions in non-perfect magnetic field environments, but also to a great extent in limited spectral purity of the ultrastable laser sources. This is despite the fact that fractional frequency instabilities on the level of 2×10^{-15} or better at 1 s averaging times have been demonstrated. Below we address the gate implementation and the laser noise.

3.1 Mølmer-Sørensen gate implementation

We summarize some general practicalities for the Mølmer-Sørensen (MS) gate as details have been published for the application of the MS scheme to optical qubits for example in [Roo08, Kir09, Ben08], and [ake15].

The MS scheme enables the realization of a maximally entangled state of an even number of qubits in ions in a shared motional state by applying bichromatic laser light globally. The 2 frequencies are symmetrically detuned slightly by δ from the red and blue motional sideband resonances of a motional mode, commonly the center-of-mass mode (COM). The gate is applied in a way that the excitation of any single ion is energetically forbidden, while the excitation of all ions at once is allowed. An additional asymmetric detuning Δ_{ac} of the bichromatic light from the undisturbed transitions is required to compensate for an ac-stark shift caused by the light's presence. During the ideal gate time τ_{gate} the qubits are first entangled with their shared motion and then fully disentangled from the motion, with only the maximal entanglement of the qubits remaining. Continuing the gate beyond that time would entangle the motion with the qubits again in a periodic fashion. Only with the right detuning δ does disentanglement from the motional mode and the 50 % excitation probability needed for a maximally entangled state (Greenberger-Horne-Zeilinger state) occur. Below a brief outline on how to choose the parameters based on experimentally easily observable quantities will be given. There will always be one parameter that can be chosen at will. A coupling strength as high as possible is chosen here as a starting point.

A measurement of the inversion time, t_{inv} , directly measured on the blue motional sideband of a single ion is used as a starting point to approximate $\tau_{\text{gate}} = t_{\text{inv}} * (N_{\text{ion}})^{-1/2}$, with N_{ion} the even number of ions in the string. This works for all motional modes in an ion-pair, but not for $N_{\text{ion}} > 2$. In that case the ions do not equally participate in the motion and couple differently to the qubit laser, so the gate won't work. The only exception is the COM mode. The symmetric detuning is then $\delta = 2\pi/\tau_{\text{gate}}$ to achieve the maximally entangled state.

The remaining parameter to be fixed is the asymmetric detuning to compensate for ac-Stark shifts. One independent way of measuring it would be to run a Ramsey experiment with a single ion and single frequency light and interleaving experiments with bichromatic light on and off during the Ramsey dark time and comparing the difference to extract the ac-Stark shift. If the bichromatic light

detuning is set to $> 5 \times \delta$ the likelihood of direct excitation of the ion is strongly reduced but has little effect on the ac-Stark shift.

This set of parameters should be close enough to reveal initial signs of entanglement and can be used as a starting point for the fine tuning with the iterative procedure described in [ake15] for the case of ion-pair entanglement. Figure 3.1, shows the typical signature for an MS gate on an ion-pair consisting of the excitation probabilities for none, either one, or both ions as function of the duration of the bichromatic pulse and parity oscillations measured at the gate time.

1. A scan of the gate time τ_{gate} to find the minimum of the probability to get exactly one bright ion.
2. A scan of the gate detuning δ to find the value where the probability for no bright ions and two bright ions are equal.
3. A scan of the ac-Stark detuning Δ_{ac} to find the minimum of the probability for exactly one bright ion.

If the initial parameter set is for each value to within 20 % of the ideal set the procedure should converge within 3 runs. For $N_{\text{ion}} > 2$ it is likely that maximizing the contrast of the parity oscillations instead of minimizing the single ion excitation probability used in the 2-ion case, will enable the use of the same iterative procedure, however theoretical and experimental evaluation have not been carried out, yet.

Figure 3.1: Entanglement signature of a 2-ion pair in the $^{88}\text{Sr}^+$ experiment at NPL. In a) Probabilities to find the ion-pair with both ions in the ground state (p_{gg}), one of the two ions in the excited state ($p_{ge} + p_{eg}$), or both ions in the excited state (p_{ee}) as function of the bichromatic pulse time. At 0.355 ms = τ_{gate} the signature for a maximally entangled ion pair, $p_{gg} = p_{ee} = 0.5$ and $p_{ge} + p_{eg} = 0$, is closely realized. In b) parity oscillations are shown. For this measurement the entanglement pulse with τ_{gate} is followed by a single $\pi/2$ pulse on the carrier transition with the phase varied relative to the entanglement pulse. Measurements (red points) of the parity, $(p_{gg} + p_{ee}) - (p_{ge} + p_{eg})$, are shown as function of the phase. A sinusoidal fit (blue line) reveals the amplitude A . The entanglement fidelity can be calculated as $F = (p_{gg} + p_{ee})/2 + A/2 = 0.96(3)$.

3.2 Local oscillators for precision spectroscopy and entanglement operations

Beyond the stability required for optical clock lasers, their use as qubit lasers for entanglement requires low frequency noise at high Fourier frequencies. During the entanglement step off-resonant noise at the motional frequency detuning from the laser carrier causes spurious excitation of the carrier and loss of fidelity.

As an example, an “ideal” 1-Hz laser with pure white frequency noise (Lorentz line shape) would have sufficient power spectral density at 1 MHz detuning to contribute to the infidelity budget with $1 - F = 1.3 \times 10^{-4}$ due to this effect alone in an otherwise ideal maximal entanglement operation setting for the NPL ion-trap based on a simple estimate following the argument in [ben09]. We identified 3 main requirements for a laser system that would enable the realization of high-fidelity entanglement and precision spectroscopy with optical qubits in trapped ions.

1. High cw power for scalable entanglement on the narrow optical qubit or clock transition.
2. Ultrastable optical frequency performance ideally outperforming the linewidth of the optical qubit transition, and
3. Ultrahigh spectral purity to minimize fast noise at the motional frequency utilized for entanglement.

In [ake15] the problem with using a clock style optical diode laser system is illustrated. Typically, locking of the lasers to ultrastable cavities with servo bandwidth matching the motional frequencies produce broad servo bumps in that range. A similar laser system was employed at LUH at 729 nm and methods to reduce the off-resonant noise at the ion explored.

E. g. filtering of the diode laser light through the optical cavity does reduce the noise by several orders of magnitude to a negligible level. However, the filtered light power is then limited to a few tens of microwatts at most. Injection locking and amplification can regain some power, but can lead to further problems, e. g. spontaneous amplified emission and unreliable injection locking.

At LUH an approach using a self-injection laser locking scheme, in which the light transmitted through a high-finesse cavity is used to inject the laser locked to the same cavity has been developed and a reduction of > 100 dB in phase noise at the relevant Fourier frequencies of a few megahertz could be demonstrated. With reliable injection locking this would make the contribution to infidelity negligible.

Alternatively, the use of titanium-sapphire lasers from 900 nm down to 670 nm can produce power at levels above 1 W in combination with low noise at high Fourier frequencies. The noise at low Fourier frequencies can be controlled to a level of at least a few $\text{Hz} \times \text{Hz}^{-1/2}$. This approach is used at NPL for ultrastable 674 nm laser light at above 1.4 W. An instability of below 1 Hz (fractional 2×10^{-15}) for 1 s to greater 100 s averaging time was verified using a frequency comb to measure against a 1064 nm laser with 1×10^{-16} performance for averaging times from 0.1 to 1000 s.

A detailed characterization of frequency noise over a wide Fourier frequency range up to several MHz was set up to evaluate the laser noise and identify narrow line features that can be detrimental to the fidelity. Figure 3.2 shows a measured spectrum of NPL’s titanium sapphire laser. Identifying those noise features can help to avoid them with appropriate setting of the entanglement parameters. In the case of the titanium sapphire laser at NPL such features around the motional frequency detuning, even if incoherently coupling to the carrier would increase the infidelity contribution to 1.7 % up from a contribution of the broad noise floor of 2×10^{-4} . More sophisticated estimates from the noise measurement results could be done using a realistic laser noise, see [Day22].

Figure 3.2: An example of the laser noise measured as frequency modulation amplitude noise with side-of-fringe measurements on 2 different optical cavities. Measurements from 0.1 Hz to about 40 kHz measurements utilize an ultrastable cavity with FWHM of 8 kHz formerly used for an $^{88}\text{Sr}^+$ optical clock [Bar07]. Above 20 kHz a medium finesse stable optical cavity with a FWHM of 1.1 MHz is used [Let04]. The amber line indicates a $1 \text{ Hz} \times \text{Hz}^{-1/2}$ resolution. An example for the measurement of the detection noise floor (taken without light applied, pale blue) is overlaid for the high frequency side where it limits the measurements above 1 MHz. The detection noise is negligible at lower frequencies. Power noise is shown in pale green. It is limiting the measurements below 10 Hz.

With the already achieved performance of the free running qubit laser further sophisticated disciplining of the low frequency laser noise out to a few kHz for the application in precision spectroscopy is feasible with the methods developed for state-of-the-art optical clocks. In case of the use of a titanium sapphire laser with its macroscopic size and associated mechanical resonances, as well as the need for regular service and running costs need to be considered. Constant monitoring of the frequency noise performance with independent in parallel to the entanglement experiments should be considered.

4. Non-classical approaches to active optical clocks

4.1 Ultimate stability of quantum limited active clocks

Active optical frequency standards provide interesting alternatives to their passive counterparts. Particularly, such a clock alone continuously generates highly stable narrow-line laser radiation. Thus, a local oscillator is not required to keep the optical phase during a dead time between interrogations as in passive clocks, but only to boost the active clock's low output power to practically usable levels with the current state of technology. In the USOQS consortium we have investigated the spectral properties and the stability of active clocks, including homogeneous and inhomogeneous broadening effects [Kaz22]. We find that for short averaging times the stability is limited by photon shot noise from the limited emitted laser power and at long averaging times by

phase diffusion of the laser output. Operational parameters for best long-term stability were identified. Using realistic numbers for an active clock with ^{87}Sr , we find that optimized stability of $\sigma_y(\tau) \approx 4 \times 10^{-18}/\sqrt{\tau}$ [s] is achievable [Kaz22].

Figure 4.1: Stability of the ^{87}Sr active clock output expressed as Allan deviation σ_y with cutoff frequency $f_h = 10$ Hz for $N = 10^4$ (blue solid line) and $N = 10^5$ (red dash-dotted line). The corresponding modified Allan deviation $\text{mod } \sigma_y$ is shown by the cyan dotted line and the yellow dotted line. The different slopes are due to contributions from photon shot noise and atomic phase diffusion. For comparison, the stability of a Dick effect limited passive clock is shown as a green dash-dot-dot line.

5. Specifications for end users building optical clocks

5.1 Rabi Oscillations – theory and experimental

The USOQS consortium developed and characterized a novel detection system for optical lattice clock with a signal-to-noise ratio and a photon scattering rate that allow for quantum non-demolition measurements, and thus for the use of spin-squeezed states in optical lattice clocks (see Deliverable D1).

This type of detection system can be beneficial to operational frequency standards in two ways. First, contributions to TAI, as reported in section 2.1, required a high degree of automation with their Sr clock systems. As such, future, regular contributions to TAI will strongly benefit from the non-destructive detection system: the large SNR offered by this scheme allow to operate the clock with a reduced number of atoms, releasing operational constraints on the optimization of the clock, as well as reducing the uncertainty on the cold-collisions frequency shift. To this aim, the detection system of WP1 was designed to be reliable, compatible with operating the clocks for extended periods of times (days or weeks). The key features of the detection enabling this reliability are the heterodyne, noise immune modulation scheme that rejects technical noises, and the cavity geometry

that ensures the quality of the mode matching (probe geometry and alignment) between the detection laser beam and the trapping laser beam.

Second, the USOQS consortium developed a theoretical proposition for a clock interrogation protocol that makes use of spin-squeezing inside a Rabi interrogation scheme (see deliverable D2), as employed in optical lattice clocks currently contributing to TAI. The gain in frequency stability achievable with this theoretical proposition (-7dB below the quantum projection noise) were estimated from the actual performances (signal-to-noise ratio and photon scattering rate) of the detection system experimentally demonstrated in WP1.

5.2 Ramsey Interrogation – theory and experimental

An obvious way to improve stability is to increase the interrogation time and thus reduce the clock linewidth. Besides the lifetime of the upper clock state that ranges to tens of seconds, the coherence time of the interrogation laser sets an even shorter limit to this time. As the phase of the laser fluctuates by more than π during the interrogation, the phase in a Rabi interrogation can no longer unambiguously be determined and reliable clock operation is no longer possible. However, using two clocks allows for much more efficient ways to reduce the influence of laser noise on the clock stability like correlated interrogations, dead-time free operation or correlation spectroscopy [Kim21]. At PTB, a method was developed that dynamically decouples laser frequency noise from the atomic excitation in a multi-pulse Ramsey excitation [Dör20]. With this method the average frequency and thus the phase error of the clock laser can be obtained over interrogation times longer than the laser coherence time. In a compound clock (see Fig. 5.1), e.g. with a single ion used in the second clock, this information can be used to extend equally the usual Ramsey interrogation with the ion and thus reduce the linewidth and improve the stability. In fact, increasing the interrogation time is the only way to improve a single ion clock. In a proof-of principle experiment at PTB, using artificially broadened laser light, an interrogation time of 0.5 s could be achieved with a laser coherence time of 77 ms.

Figure 5.1: Schematic setup of a compound clock for operation beyond the laser coherence limit. The two clocks share a common local oscillator (LO) that is pre-stabilized to an ultrastable cavity. The frequency stability of the LO is transferred to interrogation lasers, e.g. by a frequency comb (FC). Using the spectroscopic sequences shown in b, clock 1 provides a coarse estimate (ϕ_1) of the laser phase deviation to clock 2, which then refines this measurement. Their combined measured phase deviation (ϕ_{tot}) feeds back into a frequency shifter ($\Delta\nu$) to stabilize the LO frequency (taken from [Dör20]).

At NPL, a demonstration of Ramsey coherence time extension similar in essence to the above PTB approach was demonstrated making use of the quantum non-demolition (QND) readout scheme developed within USOQS [Hob19]. The QND readout allowed for a train of five Ramsey interrogations in system 1 (NPL-Sr2) to be implemented in short succession such that the phase of the clock laser could be tracked sufficiently well to extend from 300 ms to 2 s the Ramsey time in a second synchronously interrogated system (NPL-Sr1), see Fig. 5.2, reducing both the QPN- and Dick-noise contributions to the instability of its output [Bow20].

Figure 5.2: Enhanced Ramsey spectroscopy via an atom-phase-lock (APL). (a) Timing sequence for the synchronous spectroscopy scheme, and Bloch sphere representation of the atomic state during the APL sequence. Atomic data from the Rabi time in NPL-Sr1 are used only when scanning over NPL-Sr1 Ramsey fringes. Prior to and during each scan, the Rabi data measure frequency drift of the free-running LO (typically between 0 and 3 mHz/s), and allows us to apply LO drift compensation in a double-integrator control loop with attack time of approximately 100 clock cycles. (b) Results using Ramsey spectroscopy in NPL-Sr1, co-interrogated with NPL-Sr2 using the same LO. Left: excitation fractions with the LO frequency locked to the central NPL-Sr1 Ramsey fringe under three conditions: 300 ms Ramsey dark time with the APL to NPL-Sr2 disengaged (orange), 2 s dark time with the APL disengaged (red), and 2 s dark time with the APL engaged (green). Frequency scans over the NPL-Sr1 Ramsey fringes are shown on the right under the same conditions as above. With the APL engaged, the fringe width is measured to be $254(1)$ mHz for a 2 s dark time.

A similar but experimentally more challenging method involving three clocks was recently demonstrated. There, using dead-time free interrogation in two Yb clocks has been used to improve the stability of a single Al^+ ion clock to about $2 \times 10^{-16}/\sqrt{\tau}$ [Kim21].

The phase noise of the LO is a concern also when using Ramsey interrogation scheme with spin squeezed states. This problem can be readily understood by representing the squeezed clock operation on the Bloch sphere. In fact, the dephasing between the LO and the atoms occurring between the two Ramsey pulses results in a population projection on the z axes larger in the case of squeezed states if compared to classical states, thus resulting in a noisier system. To overcome

this problem, which would otherwise make it impossible to use squeezed states and reach detection noise below the Standard Quantum Limit, a novel protocol was developed within the project.

This protocol uses a hybrid system composed of a coherent (or weakly squeezed) state and one or more highly spin-squeezed atomic states interrogating, separately, the same LO [Pez20]. The coherent state allows a first estimate of the accumulated phase shift θ due to LO fluctuations that is then used to feed back a spin-squeezed atomic state toward its optimal phase-sensitivity point. The protocol can then be extended to a cascade of squeezed states that are more and more squeezed. Since the coherent state has a high dynamic range, essentially in the full interval $\theta \in [-\pi/2, \pi/2]$, in this hybrid scheme is possible to exploit squeezing also for the estimation of relatively large phase shifts associated to increasingly high phase noise of the interrogating laser, well beyond the dynamical range of squeezed states. The frequency estimate of both clocks is then combined to steer the LO frequency. In a recent proposal [Li22], the dynamical range of this scheme is further extended to $\theta \in [-\pi, \pi]$ by replacing the single coherent state in the hybrid scheme with two coherent states prepared along different directions in the Bloch sphere.

The hybrid clock overcomes the stability of a single Ramsey clock using coherent or optimal spin-squeezed states and reaches a Heisenberg-limited stability while avoiding nondestructive measurements. When using a sequence of optimal squeezed states, the hybrid quantum-classical atomic clock, surpasses the state-of-the-art proposals that exploit a cascade of Greenberger-Horne-Zeilinger, or NOON, states with different numbers of particles.

5.3 Number of atom limitation to go beyond classical limits

In a collaboration between PTB and LUH the gain in the clock stability that can be achieved using squeezing compared to the usual operation using unsqueezed, independent atoms were investigated theoretically and by simulations [Sch20]. This investigation considered realistic clocks operated with typical Brownian frequency noise-limited laser sources. For the interrogation laser, the stability of the currently most stable lasers, based on cryogenic silicon cavities [Mat17] was assumed. Based on a model of the closed servo-loop of an optical atomic clock, quantitative predictions on the optimal clock stability for a given dead time and laser noise were derived.

Figure 5.2: Optimized stability of a clock with unsqueezed (CSS) and squeezed (SSS) ensemble as a function of the atom number for different dead times T_D of the clock interrogation cycle (taken from [Sch20]).

For usual periodic Ramsey interrogation of single atomic ensembles with dead time for atom cooling and trapping and detection, and even with the current most stable lasers, spin squeezing can only improve the clock stability for ensembles below a critical atom number of about one thousand in an optical Sr lattice clock (see Fig. 5.2). Even with a future improvement of the laser performance by one order of magnitude the critical atom number still remains below 100 000.

In contrast, clocks based on smaller, non-scalable ensembles, such as ion clocks, already with current clock lasers, would benefit from using squeezed states. In particular, arrays of up to 1000 atoms trapped in magic-wavelength optical tweezers have recently emerged as an alternative platform for optical atomic clocks, with work on number-resolved detection carried out within our consortium at UDUR [Jac20]. Bi-partite entanglement has been generated with high fidelity using the long-range interaction between atoms in Rydberg states, and a path appears open to creating squeezed states in this fashion.

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